

An Analysis of the CNR Call for Senior Technologist

Giorgio Luciano^{1}, Roberto Salzano^{2*}, Salvatore Aronica³, Giuseppe Marsala⁴, Fiorella Sarubbi^{5**}*

¹ Institute of Chemical Sciences and Technologies "Giulio Natta", National Research Council, Italy;

² Institute of Atmospheric Pollution Research, National Research Council, Italy; ³ Institute for the Study of Anthropogenic Impacts and Sustainability in the Marine Environment, National Research Council, Italy; ⁴ Institute of Marine Engineering, National Research Council, Italy, ⁵ Institute for the Animal Production System in the Mediterranean Environment, National Research Council, Italy

**These authors contributed equally to the work*

***Author for correspondence: e-mail: fiorella.sarubbi@cnr.it*

Introduction

The public research evaluation system in Italy has been undergoing a phase of profound revision for years, suspended between a tradition still linked to quantitative bibliometric indicators and new European rules calling for their replacement by promoting a quality-based approach. The latest competition calls from the National Research Council (CNR), issued in 2023 for the career progression of 210 Technologists from the III to the II professional level, constitute an interesting case study to understand how these two paradigms still coexist, and sometimes clash, in the administrative practice of a large Public Research Organization.

The selective procedure in question was divided into ten competition sectors (Table 1), and saw the respective examining committees deal with a qualitative evaluation mandate inspired by European standards.

The criteria and evaluations reflected the specificities of each disciplinary field, leading to varied application strategies across different sectors. The analysis of this call aims to focus on three fundamental issues: how a Technologist is evaluated compared to a Researcher; what the eventual limits of committee autonomy are; and if and how much Italy is implementing international principles on research assessment reform.

Table 1 - Competition sectors provided by the calls (Sectors 01 to 10 ranging from Earth System Sciences to Decision-making and management processes of the Institution).

Code	COMPETITION SECTOR
01	Management, support and valorization of research and innovation activities in the field of Earth System Sciences and Environmental Technologies
02	Management, support, and enhancement of research and innovation activities in the Bio-Agri-Food Sciences sector
03	Management, support, and enhancement of research and innovation activities in the field of Chemical Sciences and Materials Technologies
04	Management, support and valorization of research and innovation activities in the field of Physical Sciences and Matter Technologies
05	Management, support and valorization of research and innovation activities in the Biomedical Sciences sector
06	Management, support and valorization of research and innovation activities in the Engineering, ICT and Energy and Transport Technologies sectors
07	Management, support and valorization of research and innovation activities in the field of Human and Social Sciences, Cultural Heritage
08	Management of Research Infrastructures, Laboratories and Plants, Digital Technologies for Research or other Facilities with Scientific Purposes
09	Valorization and Promotion of Research Results and Technical and Scientific Support to Institutions
10	Decision-making and management processes of the Institution

The Evaluation Structure: Titles and Interview

The Scoring System: 100 Total Points

The evaluation system provided a total maximum score of 100 points, distributed over three main components: the evaluation of the professional curriculum (max 70 points), the valorization of seniority acquired at CNR (max 10 points), and the individual interview (max 20 points). To be included in the final merit ranking, it was necessary to obtain a minimum score of 60/100.

This access threshold functioned as a qualitative filter, giving a decisive weight to the documentary dimension of the career.

The Four Sections of the Professional Curriculum

The professional curriculum vitae had to be divided into four sections, each with a specific weight and for a total of 70 points out of 100, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2 – Curricular evaluation sections

Section	Max points	% of total
Section 1: Products and Selected Titles	30	30%
Section 2: Contribution and results of activity	25	25%
Section 3: Perspectives and potential	5	5%
Section 4: Professional path	10	10%
Professional CV Score	70	70%

Seniority and Interview

Seniority in the current professional level was evaluated proportionally up to a maximum of 10 points. This was followed by an oral interview with a maximum score of 20 points (Table 3).

Table 3 – Breakdown of evaluation and interview scores

Evaluation of CNR activities (seniority)	10	10%
Interview	20	20%
Value and Total score	30	30%

Final score

The two main sections (Curriculum and Valorization) led to the final score, as summarized below (table 4).

Table 4 – Total final score

Professional CV	70	70%
Appraisal and Interview	30	30%
Final Score	100	100%

Titles for Sections 1, 2, and 4 had to be acquired by **December 31, 2022**, to ensure equal conditions among candidates

This decision, which fixed the curriculum vitae on a specific date, was intended to ensure equal conditions and uniform treatment among candidates by establishing a common timeframe, within a procedural framework structured across multiple competition sessions over the three-year period 2023-2025.

The Interview as a Moment to Verify Perspectives

The interview was not a test of disciplinary knowledge but a short dissertation on the candidate's professional experiences. The committee was tasked with assessing the candidates' objectives, autonomy, future perspectives, and capacity to implement innovative models, thereby evaluating their future potential alongside past achievements.

The Evaluation of Products and Titles: A Heterogeneous Evaluation Landscape

In Section 1, each candidate selected up to 15 products or titles (from a list of 30 previously submitted). The committee assigned an analytical score to each, up to a maximum of 2 points, for a total of 30 points. The framework revealed greater consistency among committees and greater respect for CoARA principles compared to other processes, especially in the broader evaluation of all types of titles and products (Table 5).

Table 5 – List of products and titles foreseen by the tender

PRODUCTS (P1 - P11)		TITLES (T1 - T27)	
P1	Journal Contribution	T1	Scientific responsibility for international and national research projects, admitted to funding based on competitive calls that include peer review
P2	Volume Contribution [chapter, essay, preface/afterword, introduction, dictionary or encyclopedia entry], translation, review, catalog entry]	T2	Responsibility for archaeological survey/excavation campaign
P3	Book (scientific monograph or treatise; critical edition; edited volume or treatise with chapter, publication of unpublished sources; book translation)	T3	Research Infrastructure Responsibility
P4	Contribution to Conference Proceedings and Posters	T4	Participation in international and national research projects, eligible for funding based on competitive calls for proposals that include peer review.
P5	Patents	T5	Participation in archaeological survey/excavation campaign
P6	Database, Software, Data set	T6	Participation in research infrastructure

P7	Projects and prototypes (drawings; technical design reports; architectural projects; design works; instrumentation prototypes; art prototypes and related projects)	T7	Responsible for technical/scientific studies or research groups
P8	Exhibition; Show; Multimedia application or product (video documentary)	T8	Assignment of research assignments (fellowships) at research institutions
P9	Cartographic product or map	T9	Institute Management
P10	Concordance; index; critical or annotated bibliography; scientific commentary	T10	University teaching positions
P11	Report or Technical Report (report published in a scientific institution's repository or sent to internal or external clients; deliverables of national or international projects)	T11	Participation in evaluation and monitoring commissions of research programs and projects, and of research institutions
		T12	Management positions in national and international associations, foundations, and scientific societies
		T13	Participation in national or international technical-scientific or managerial bodies and organizations
		T14	Management of scientific journals and series
		T15	Coordination of national or international scientific conferences or events
		T16	Participation in editorial boards and scientific and editorial committees (Editorial Board) of national or international journals/series, encyclopedias
		T17	Awarding of "ERC Grants" or other national and international prizes and/or awards awarded by particularly important and prestigious scientific institutions, including affiliation with academies of recognized prestige in the field
		T18	Invited lectures / Keynotes at national and international conferences
		T19	Technical-scientific consultancy and support assignments
		T20	Scientific diplomacy positions and/or Scientific Attaché positions at diplomatic representations and international organizations, support to European institutions as a Seconded National Expert
		T21	Certification activities

T22	Activation and participation of start-ups and spin-offs
T23	Organization of public engagement initiatives and events
T24	Technical and management roles within the organization (responsibility or coordination of a laboratory, experimental apparatus, or other scientifically relevant structure, management responsibility for a research project or program, and sole responsibility for the procedure for tenders above the EU threshold for scientific instrumentation)
T25	Highly professional organizational positions (e.g. DPO, RSPP, Laser Safety Technician, Radiation Protection, Competent Physician)
T26	National Scientific Qualification
T27	Supervision of doctoral students
T28	Internal management roles within the organization (e.g., responsibility for administrative structures, delegation of managerial functions)
T29	Technical-administrative roles (RUP, Personnel Selection Procedure Manager, Project Management, Safety Coordinator during the design or execution phase, Contract Execution Management, Administrative Procedure Managers, and others not mentioned to be specified)

The study of the scores assigned to the different products for the PT competition was investigated using the resulting variability (between maximum and minimum) for all disciplinary sectors, as well as the distribution described by the 25% (first quartile - Q1), 50% (Median), and 75% (third quartile - Q3) of the scores assigned to each product. While the gap between Q1 and Q3 of the scores assigned by each committee is an indicator of the consensus in recognizing the value of the product or qualification, the median identifies the tendency of the committees to reward certain types rather than others. Outliers are those scores that statistically deviate from many of the scores assigned to each individual product by the committees.

Fig.1 Statistical distribution of scores assigned by committees for each type of product

As can be verified in Figure 1, for technologists, the class of conventional products (contributions to journals, book chapters, and books) in addition to patents, datasets, software, and prototypes, showed greater consistency, with the gap remaining at 2 points.

All the remaining products, including conference contributions, have high variability, with a median that is nevertheless shifted towards the maximum score.

The general convergence of the 10 committees in evaluating the products is consistent, with few peculiarities on specific products.

For the qualifications, there are 10 most significant elements in which the assigned score agrees on the maximum: and they are T1, T2, T3, T7, T9, T14, T17, T20, T22, and T24. In the remaining cases, the committees do not agree in assigning the scores; among these, the most penalized elements turn out to be T4, T5, T6, and T27 (Figure 2).

Fig.2 Statistical distribution of scores assigned by the commissions for each type of Title.

From the analysis of the criteria established by the committees of the ten competition sectors, a differentiated picture emerged, reflecting the plurality of evaluation approaches adopted in the various disciplinary fields. First, the number of judgment components, which in 60-70% of cases had been structured into 3-4 evaluation criteria. Half of the committees had an open judgment on patents, while only one maintained the same attitude towards various unconventional products (Figure 3).

Fig.3 Frequency of the number of judging components selected by the commissions for each product type.

In general, the committees adopted three distinct types of evaluation approaches.

Approaches Compared

The analysis of the criteria established by the ten committees revealed four distinct types of evaluative approaches. Sectors 01, 02, 05, and 10 based their evaluation on a grid of four criteria, each weighted 0.5 points: Originality and innovativeness, Technological relevance and quality, Impact on the organization (efficiency, best practices), and the candidate's specific role. This model is the most consistent with the Technologist profile, which is contractually oriented towards the technological and organizational valorization of research.

With respect to the general guidelines of the call, three sectors deemed it appropriate to integrate quantitative parameters into the evaluation of research products (Sectors 03, 04, 06). Specifically, the "Chemical Sciences and Materials Technologies" Sector took scientific relevance into consideration also as a function of bibliometric indices; the "Physical Sciences" Sector chose to include citations and indicators provided by the candidates in the evaluations, while the "Engineering and ICT" Sector estimated the scientific impact by using the bibliometric indicators commonly in use in the respective communities of reference.

These methodological choices reflect the established traditions in the respective disciplinary fields, in line with the CNR directive recommending a responsible, but not mandatory, use of bibliometric indicators. The choice to maintain bibliometric criteria in these fields reflects the established approach in the sectors of physics, chemistry, and engineering, historically linked to internationally shared metrics, such as the number of citations and Journal Impact Factors, whose transition towards new evaluation paradigms physiologically requires gradual processes.

The Area dedicated to "Research Infrastructures and Digital Technologies" (sector 08) adopted intermediate solutions. Three criteria were used (Relevance, Impact, Role) with scores from 0 to 1, but the theoretical sum could exceed 2 points and was, therefore, capped at the established maximum. This system can be considered technically valid, but it reflects an evaluative choice oriented towards rewarding excellence in the criteria deemed most relevant for the profile, regardless of the distribution of the contribution among the different parameters.

Sectors 03, 06, 07, and 09 simplified the evaluation into two criteria: one linked to Originality/Impact/Relevance and one dedicated to the Role, each up to 1 point. While allowing for a holistic evaluation, this approach reduced granularity.

Procedural Specifics: Differing Caps and Role Incidence

Beyond the different general methodological approaches, the practical application of the criteria highlighted some specific heterogeneities. These procedural adaptations reflected the specific operational customs of each scientific field, balancing general guidelines with the evaluative autonomy recognized by the committees.

The most significant one concerned the implicit hierarchization of the products. The call did not provide for any differentiation in the maximum value attributable to different types of products: each chosen product could be worth up to 2 points; however, some committees introduced specific determinations of lower ceilings:

- Sector 04: books limited to 1.5 points; conference proceedings limited to 1 point
- Sector 03: conference proceedings at 1 point; exhibitions, maps, indexes at only 0.5 points

This option, although motivated by the specificities of the individual scientific fields, introduced a modulation of the scores consistent with the disciplinary specificities of the respective sectors, within the scope of the evaluative autonomy recognized to the committees. Consequently, the inclusion of conference proceedings or monographs among the 15 evaluable products led to a differentiated application of the criteria, consistent with the evaluation customs of the individual disciplinary fields for such editorial types.

A similar dynamic was found in the weighting attributed to the candidate's role within the publications. In Sectors 01, 05, and 10, the individual contribution accounted for 25% of the score of the single product (equal to 0.5 points out of 2); in Sector 09, this incidence was set at 50% (1 point out of 2), while in Sector 06, the possible absence of a role considered leading could result in a modulation of the score up to 0.2 points.

Everything is summarized in the following table 6.

Table 6 - Comparison of evaluative approaches by competition sector

Sector	Approach	Main criteria	Critical notes	Consistency
01, 02, 05, 10	Qualitative parameters) (4	Originality, relevance, organizational impact, role (0.5 points each)	Model most suited to the Technologist profile	Fully aligned
03, 04, 06	Bibliometric	Includes bibliometric indices	Lowering the ceilings: books 1.5 points, conferences 1 point	Sector-specific adaptation
08, 09	Saturation/variable sum	3 or 2 criteria with a maximum cap of 2 points	Simplified scoring structure focused on core criteria	Aligned with qualitative parameters

The Value of the Narrative Curriculum

A profile of particular significance, which required a significant interpretative effort on the part of the candidates, is represented by the descriptive-narrative component of the curriculum. Sections 2 (Contribution and results of the activity), 3 (Perspectives and potential), and 4 (Professional path) assigned, overall, a maximum of 40 points — a significant share of the entire evaluation — and were subject to a qualitative weighting. These sections did not focus on the mere listing of publications, but rather on the ability to illustrate the coherence of one's professional path and the related development perspectives.

This evaluation model values reflective and project-based reporting skills that complement traditional scientific production. Knowing how to articulate the motivations of one's research lines, the impact generated for the Institution, and future goals represents a methodological attitude that today assumes a centrality equal to that of the actual scientific investigation activity itself.

The transition towards qualitative evaluation: opportunities and development perspectives

The Institution's adherence to the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment initiates an important methodological evolution which, while requiring a physiological gradualness in its full implementation (as evidenced by the coexistence of bibliometric approaches in specific fields), opens up new perspectives for professional profiles whose contributions were only partially captured by traditional quantitative indicators. Technologists and researchers involved in the management of research infrastructures, in software development, in the creation of databases, in the enhancement of

cultural heritage, or in the coordination of organizational processes now have, on a programmatic level, enhancement criteria that mirror those provided for high-impact editorial production.

The configuration of this new paradigm requires, however, the adoption of shared metrics and reference parameters. The development of shared definitions for concepts such as "originality", "impact", or "excellence" would represent a useful tool to further strengthen the application consistency among the different committees. The challenge for the coming years — both for the CNR and for the entire system of Public Research Institutions — therefore lies in the development of evaluation frameworks capable of combining the enhancement of qualitative aspects with the requirements of transparency, fairness, and procedural comparability.

Conclusion

The call for applications for Senior Technologist represented a useful case study for analyzing the evolutionary dynamics of the Italian research assessment system. On one hand, the procedure incorporated international guidelines aimed at moving beyond bibliometrics as an exclusive criterion, promoting the enhancement of the plurality of professional contributions. On the other hand, its practical implementation reflected the different methodological traditions of the individual sectors, highlighting the intrinsic complexity of translating general guidelines into specific operational criteria.

For the personnel of Public Research Institutions (EPR), this scenario requires a dual focus: a thorough knowledge of the formal requirements of the procedure — such as deadlines, scores, and the structure of the call — and, simultaneously, a detailed analysis of the specific criteria adopted by the individual committees, which reflect the specificities and customs of the different competition fields.

The evolution of research assessment models constitutes an articulate process that goes beyond the formal transposition of international agreements. It requires constant commitment in terms of transparency, methodological sharing, and constructive dialogue among the different components of the scientific system. The experience gained in this procedure confirms the complexity of this transition, while highlighting that the path of renewal is now underway.

References

- <https://www.coara.org/agreement/guiding-principles/>
- https://archivio.urp.cnr.it/copertine/formazione/form_concorsi/concorsi2023/315_65_bando.pdf
- https://archivio.urp.cnr.it/copertine/formazione/form_concorsi/concorsi2023/315_65_bando_rett.pdf
- https://archivio.urp.cnr.it/copertine/formazione/form_concorsi/concorsi2023/315_65_criteri_01.pdf
- https://archivio.urp.cnr.it/copertine/formazione/form_concorsi/concorsi2023/315_65_criteri_02.pdf
- https://archivio.urp.cnr.it/copertine/formazione/form_concorsi/concorsi2023/315_65_criteri_03.pdf

- https://archivio.urp.cnr.it/copertine/formazione/form_concorsi/concorsi2023/315_65_criteri_04.pdf
- https://archivio.urp.cnr.it/copertine/formazione/form_concorsi/concorsi2023/315_65_criteri_05.pdf
- https://archivio.urp.cnr.it/copertine/formazione/form_concorsi/concorsi2023/315_65_criteri_06.pdf
- https://archivio.urp.cnr.it/copertine/formazione/form_concorsi/concorsi2023/315_65_criteri_07.pdf
- https://archivio.urp.cnr.it/copertine/formazione/form_concorsi/concorsi2023/315_65_criteri_08.pdf
- https://archivio.urp.cnr.it/copertine/formazione/form_concorsi/concorsi2023/315_65_criteri_09.pdf
- https://archivio.urp.cnr.it/copertine/formazione/form_concorsi/concorsi2023/315_65_criteri_10.pdf